

Interaction of spermine with DNA, vitamin C and bovine serum albumin in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states^ψ

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Abstract : Structural deformability of spermine with radiation dose (maximum 10 Gy) has been proved. Complex formation of spermine with DNA, vitamin C and BSA took place. Calibration and radiation-induced absorption changes in spermine by ninhydrin reagent has been followed quantitatively. Interaction of vitamin C with DNA and their radiation-induced changes have been reported. Interaction of spermine with DNA in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states in 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer and water have been compared. Addition of spermine and vitamin C to DNA makes DNA structure more condensed. Bovine serum albumin also binds with spermine and protects it from radiation-induced degradation.

Keywords : DNA, spermine, gamma irradiation, bovine serum albumin, vitamin C.

Spermine protects DNA and this influences the structure and condensation of chromatin¹. However, it affects normal DNA synthesis². Mechanism of protection by spermine includes protection of DNA from enzymatic degradation, binding with human serum albumin, interaction with mammalian DNA and topoisomerase II. Thus it is capable of protecting lymphoma cells from radiation-induced apoptosis³. To increase the efficacy of protection vitamin C has been used earlier, as it protects against carcinogenesis in rats^{4,5}.

So, interaction of spermine with DNA, vitamin C and bovine serum albumin in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states have been undertaken in this study.

Results

IR spectral characteristics of spermine (1 mM) in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated (dose rate 0.0065 Gy/s) states clearly indicates a consistent decrease in % *T* from 6–10 Gy when compared to unirradiated value (Table 1). $A_{231\text{ nm}}$ and $A_{257\text{ nm}}$ values increased linearly with increase in spermine concentration from 1 to 9×10^{-8} M in 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer when spermine was complexed with ninhydrin reagent. In the pH range of 6.70–6.80 in 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer $A_{232\text{ nm}}$ and $A_{258\text{ nm}}$ values for ninhydrin reagent consistently decreased with radiation dose up to 20

Gy when compared to unirradiated values. The $A_{232\text{ nm}}$ values and its decrease with dose for irradiated solutions (dose rate 0.0064 Gy/s) were more compared to that at $A_{258\text{ nm}}$. In water, when ninhydrin reagent was complexed with spermine it showed an absorption maximum at 560 nm. The $A_{560\text{ nm}}$ values decreased with dose (dose rate 0.96 Gy/s) linearly up to 100 Gy.

The positions of absorption maxima at 232 nm and 257 nm of the complex of spermine with ninhydrin did not change with radiation dose up to 300 Gy. The $A_{232\text{ nm}}$ and $A_{257\text{ nm}}$ values increased consistently with dose up to 500 Gy at a dose rate of 3.72 Gy/h (Table 2). At a dose rate of 0.006 Gy/s, the $A_{263\text{ nm}} - A_{268\text{ nm}}$ values of vitamin C (7.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) showed increased absorption intensity compared to unirradiated vitamin C (3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Even if 7.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration of vitamin C were taken the absorption intensity at 267 nm would have been 0.75. So, at a dose of 2.5 Gy itself maximum absorption intensity was observed ($A_{263\text{ nm}} = 1.45$), but as the dose increased there was a gradual fall in absorbance intensity with increase in dose ($A_{268\text{ nm}}$ for 5 Gy = 1.18, for 10 Gy = 0.88). When to a low concentration of vitamin C (1×10^{-5} g/ml) increasing concentration of spermine was added and irradiated to 5 Gy at a dose rate of

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0.0061 Gy/s in 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer the $A_{264\text{ nm}}$ values did not change much (Table 3). When to 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of DNA increasing concentration of spermine was added a plateau ranging from 255 nm to 265 nm was obtained. The $A_{260\text{ nm}}$ values increased consistently with increasing concentration of spermine in 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer. The pH values did not change much. When to 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of DNA increasing concentration of spermine was added in 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer, pH range 6.44–6.60 and irradiated to a dose of 5 Gy at a dose rate of 0.0061 Gy/s, $A_{260\text{ nm}}$ values increased consistently (Table 4). With water as solvent also, when to 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of DNA increasing concentration of spermine was added a blue-shift was observed. There was a linear increase in absorbance intensity at absorbance maximum values with increase in concentration of spermine. By addition of spermine to DNA increase in pH was observed. When to a fixed concentration of DNA (12.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) increasing concentration of vitamin C was added the absorbance intensity at absorbance maximum increased linearly. Vitamin C alone showed an absorption maximum at 263 nm and DNA showed at 260 nm. The pH value ranged between 5.78 to 6.00 for the complexes and that for vitamin C and DNA were 5.62 and 6.13 respectively. When to 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of DNA increasing concentration of spermine and increasing concentration of vitamin C were added in 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer absorption maxima position (260–265 nm) did not change but its intensity consistently increased in the pH range of 6.68–6.78 (Table 5). To bovine serum albumin (250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) increasing concentration of spermine was added and by that the absorption intensity at 275 nm increased marginally but there was consistent increase in pH values. The complexes of BSA with spermine formed earlier when were irradiated to 10 Gy at a dose rate of 0.0059 Gy/s hyperchromicity at 275 nm was relatively much more compared to unirradiated. The pH increase was in conformity with increase in concentration of spermine.

Discussions

The structural formula of spermine is : $-\text{H}_2\text{N}-(\text{CH}_2)_3-\text{NH}-(\text{CH}_2)_4-\text{NH}-(\text{CH}_2)_3-\text{NH}_2$. IR spectra of spermine (concentration 1 mM) with increase in radiation dose clearly indicates (percentage transmittance values at 1665 cm^{-1}) increasing vulnerability of $-\text{NH}_2$ and NH groups of the molecule with dose (Table 1) as the bond energy for $\text{C}-\text{NH}_2$ is 69.7 kcal/mol^6 .

Low level detection of spermine in the physiological

pH range of 6.56–6.65 by ninhydrin reagent is helpful for cellular studies. The concentration of complex of spermine with ninhydrin has increased linearly in the spermine concentration range of $1-9 \times 10^{-8}$ M. So, stability of ninhydrin reagent was tested against radiation dose. The chromophores

increasing radiation dose thereby lowering absorbance intensity at 232 nm and 258 nm up to 20 Gy.

Table 1. The IR spectral characteristics of spermine in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states

Concentration of spermine : 1 mM; dose rate : 0.0065 Gy/s				
Unirradiated/ irradiated (Gy)	Wave number (cm^{-1})	% T	Assignment	
Unirradiated	1665	80%	NH ₃ deformation asymmetric	
	1650–1670 (Sharp peak)			
1	500–2500	~0		
2	(No peak)	~0		
4	500–2500 (No peak)	84% throughout		
6	1650–1670	72%	NH ₃ deformation asymmetric	
8	1665 (1650–1670)	56%	NH ₃ deformation asymmetric	
10	1665 (1650–1670)	27%	NH ₃ deformation asymmetric	

But the complex of spermine (5×10^{-8} M) with ninhydrin reagent (4×10^{-3} g/ml) was found to be hyperchromic (80% at 232 nm and 184% at 257 nm at 500 Gy) with increasing radiation dose at a dose rate of 3.72 kGy/h (Table 2).

Table 2. UV absorption spectral characteristics of spermine in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states as detected by ninhydrin reagent

Concentration of spermine : 5×10^{-8} M; volume of ninhydrin reagent : 5 μL ; dose rate : 3.72 kGy/h; solvent : 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer

Unirradiated/ irradiated (Gy)	$\lambda_{\text{max}1}$ (nm)	$A_{\lambda_{\text{max}1}}$	$\lambda_{\text{max}2}$ (nm)	$A_{\lambda_{\text{max}2}}$
Unirradiated	232	0.30	257	0.19
50	232	0.32	257	0.30
100	232	0.38	257	0.32
200	232	0.44	257	0.34
300	232	0.51	257	0.34
400	232	0.52 (no peak)	257	0.40
500	232	0.54 (no peak)	257	0.54

After binding with spermine the chromophores of ninhydrin were less susceptible to radiation dose up to 300 Gy beyond which loosening of bonds took place thereby showing absence of peak at 232 nm and abrupt increase in $A_{257\text{ nm}}$ values. Radiation-induced changes of the complex of spermine with ninhydrin have been depicted in Table 2.

Increased hyperchromicity with dose up to 300 Gy at 257 nm and 232 nm were obtained, the maximum values at these two λ_{max} were 79% and 70% respectively. This reflects instability of the complex of spermine with ninhydrin with respect to radiation dose (Table 2).

The λ_{max} at 267 nm for vitamin C in the unirradiated state is due to the chromophor and is due to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition⁷.

At a radiation dose of 2.5 Gy itself exposition of chromophores took place to the maximum extent. The nature of chromophor has also changed thereby a blue shift ($\lambda_{max} = 263 \text{ nm}$) has occurred. With further increase in dose the chromophores have been destructed thereby reducing absorbance intensity.

Table 3. Effect of gamma irradiation on vitamin C + spermine irradiated to 5 Gy

Dose rate : 0.0061 Gy/s; solvent : 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer			
Vitamin C (g/ml)	Spermine ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	$A_{264 \text{ nm}}$	pH
1×10^{-5}	1.01	0.103	6.33
1×10^{-5}	2.02	0.113	6.54
1×10^{-5}	3.03	0.109	6.56
1×10^{-5}	4.04	0.113	6.57
1×10^{-5}	5.05	0.137	6.42

Possible breakdown products of vitamin C chromophor by gamma radiation are shown below :

Possible breakdown products

The maximum change in $A_{264 \text{ nm}}$ for a spermine concentration of $5.05 \mu\text{g/ml}$ to vitamin C ($1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g/ml}$) was by 0.034 absorbance unit. The maximum change in pH was by 0.24 unit. By mixing there can be electron capture by vitamin C donated by $-\text{NH}_2$ groups of spermine. At this dose of 5 Gy there may not be very much disruption in the additive compound of vitamin C with spermine (Table 3). DNA forms a charge neutralization complex with spermine. While spermine has got no absorption maximum, that for DNA it is at 260 nm. This is due to $-\text{C}=\text{C}=\text{N}-$ chromophor. The negative charges of the phosphate groups of DNA get neutralized by the positive charges of spermine¹. Total number of binding sites in $50 \mu\text{g/ml}$ of DNA get neutralized by the positive charges of spermine, Total number of binding sites in $50 \mu\text{g/ml}$ of DNA is quite high which has not been filled up by the highest concentration of spermine used. The broadness of absorption maximum (255–265 nm) is an evidence of slow filling up of binding sites.

The intermediate concentrations of spermine when mixed with $50 \mu\text{g/ml}$ DNA showed close $A_{260 \text{ nm}}$ values in the unirradiated and 5 Gy irradiated states. The binding of spermine (+4 positive charge) with negatively charged DNA is by charge neutralization. Even at a low concentration intra and intermolecular condensation of spermine with DNA occurred⁵. The nature of binding is strong enough not to get dissociated at 5 Gy dose.

Table 4. UV absorption spectral parameters of DNA mixed with increasing concentration of spermine

Solvent : 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer				
Concentration of DNA ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Concentration of spermine ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	pH	λ_{max} (nm)	$A_{\lambda_{max}}$
50	0	6.81	260	0.46
50	1.01	6.82	260	0.66
50	2.02	6.84	260	0.70
50	3.03	6.86	260	0.70
50	4.04	6.87	260	0.76

Table 5. UV absorption spectral parameters of DNA mixed with vitamin C and spermine

Solvent : 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer; pH : 6.68–6.78						
DNA ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) + spermine ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) + vitamin C (10^{-4} g/ml)						
					λ_{max} (nm)	$A_{\lambda_{max}}$
20	+	0.034	+	0.083	260–265	0.15
20	+	0.068	+	0.166	260–265	0.21
20	+	0.102	+	0.249	260–265	0.28
20	+	0.136	+	0.332	260–265	0.32
20	+	0.170	+	0.415	260–265	0.39

The binding of spermine with DNA in water again gave an evidence of DNA condensation with increasing concentration of spermine. The blue-shift from 258 nm for DNA to lower wavelength for different DNA-spermine complexes are direct evidences of filling up of binding sites of DNA. As a result interaction of increasing concentration of vitamin C with fixed concentration of DNA, the position of absorption maximum at 258–260 nm did not change but $A_{\lambda_{max}}$ showed a linear increase. There was chromophoric interaction between $-\text{C}=\text{C}=\text{N}-$ of DNA and chromophor of vitamin C thereby increasing $A_{258 \text{ nm}} - A_{260 \text{ nm}}$ values. Table 5 clearly indicates interaction of DNA ($20 \mu\text{g/ml}$) with increasing concentration of spermine and vitamin C. The broadness of absorption maximum has been narrowed down from 255–265 nm for DNA-spermine interaction by addition of vitamin C to 260–265 nm. Almost a linear increase has been occurred by the addition of multiplied concentrations of spermine and vitamin C compared to first concentration. Mechanism of interaction of spermine with DNA and vitamin C has been already explained. This is a

cumulative effect that has been observed here (Table 5). Bovine serum albumin showed an absorption maximum at 275 nm due to the presence of tryptophan, phenylalanine and tyrosine. As spermine doses not show any absorption maximum its increase in concentration may induce interaction of carboxylic acid groups (e.g. lysine, arginine etc.) with the NH and NH₂ groups of spermine. Basicity has increased in the interaction with increase in concentration of spermine. Increase in hyperchromicity for the complexes of BSA with different concentrations of spermine for 10 Gy irradiated samples compared to unirradiated are due to the dissociation of the complexes of BSA-spermine after irradiation.

Experimental

Spermine (S3256), DNA (1501) and bovine serum albumin (A2153) were obtained from Sigma Chemical Company. Vitamin C was obtained from Sarabhai Pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd. Ninhydrin was obtained from Qualigens (Glaxo), India. Trisodium citrate and citric acid were from E. Merck and Company.

IR spectral studies of solutions of spermine in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states were carried out in FT-IR equipment (Bio-Rad, USA, Model FTs 40). Absorbance measurements of solutions in the unirradiated and differently gamma irradiated states were carried out in 1 cm cuvettes in a UV-visible 916 GBC spectrophotometer (Made in Australia).

Accuracy of absorbance 0.001 unit. pH values of solutions were measured by Toshniwal pH meter, Chandigarh up to an accuracy of ± 0.01 unit. Irradiation of solutions for low dose were carried out in Gamma Cell 220 (Model GC 220) at a dose rate of 0.0065 Gy/s. For high dose, irradiation were carried out in gamma chamber 5000 at a dose rate of 3.74 kGy/hr. Low dose rate was determined by FBX dosimetry⁸, and high dose rate by Fricke dosimetry⁹.

Two stock solutions of (conc. 2670 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were prepared in water and 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer from which required concentrations were prepared by suitable dilution with respective solvent. Similarly two stock solutions of DNA (conc. 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were prepared in water and 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer from which required concentrations were prepared by suitable dilution with respective solvent. Vitamin C stock solution was prepared in water at a concentration of 25 mg/ml. Bovine serum albumin was dissolved in water at a concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ from which required concentration was prepared by dilution. Ninhydrin reagent

was prepared at a concentration of 0.4% in acetone. Different sets of solutions as given in Tables were prepared by suitable mixing of solvents or reagents or compounds to achieve the desired concentrations indicated. Irradiation of solutions (5 ml) were done in pyrex test tubes of uniform diameter and 1 mm thickness.

Conclusion :

Spermine binds with DNA, vitamin C and bovine serum albumin. By thus binding radiation-induced deformation of spermine is hindered. Hence this combination should be used for radioprotection purpose.

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